

MODULATING THE GLYCEMIC INDEX AND GLYCEMIC LOAD OF JAME-SHIRIN THROUGH ISPAGHULA HUSK INTERVENTION

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Mr. Abdur Rehman**Abstract**

Background: The increasing consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages (SSBs) heightens the risk of diabetes and adversely affects the cardiometabolic system. The prevalence of diabetes worldwide has surged, and Pakistan ranked third globally in terms of diabetes prevalence in 2021. Various factors contributing to this surge including genetics, environmental influences, inactive lifestyles, obesity, and dietary habits. The glycemic index (GI) and glycemic load (GL) play pivotal roles in managing hyperglycemia. Low GI foods exhibit a slower glucose response, contrasting high GI foods that elevate glucose levels rapidly. GL combines the quality and quantity of carbohydrates in a food serving, offering a complete assessment of glycemic impact. Increasing dietary fiber intake has been recommended to mitigate glycemic responses. Yet, limited information exists on GI and GL values for commonly consumed Pakistani beverages.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate the impact of dietary fiber, specifically ispaghula husk (Psyllium Husk), on the GI and GL of Jam-e-Shirin, a prevalent Pakistani beverage.

Methodology: Fifteen healthy male participants with normal BMI and blood pressure were enrolled in a non-blind interventional study. Over six months, participants were subjected to a regimen of Jam-e-Shirin and fiber, with reference glucose as the control. Blood glucose levels were monitored at specific intervals. GI and GL values were calculated using the trapezoid method and analyzed using the Paired T-Test in SPSS.

Results: The study revealed significant reductions in GI and GL with the addition of dietary fiber. Group 2, receiving 5.0 grams of fiber, exhibited the most pronounced effect in lowering both GI and GL.

Conclusion: Incorporating dietary fiber, specifically ispaghula husk, into Jam-e-Shirin effectively lowered its GI and GL. This finding offers a valuable dietary strategy for managing glycemic responses, particularly relevant for individuals with diabetes or at risk of developing the condition.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a metabolic disorder that causes elevated blood glucose levels (1) and manifests in two primary forms: Type 1 Diabetes, characterized by insufficient pancreatic insulin production, and Type 2 Diabetes, the cells of our body cannot properly respond to insulin (2). The increased utilization of sugar-sweetened beverages (SSB) including soft drinks, fruit drinks, sports drink, and different types of locally used drinks increase the chances of diabetes and also have a deleterious effect on the cardiometabolic system of the body (3). Diabetes is one of the major causes of death worldwide with its prevalence steadily increasing over recent decades. (4) The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reported that in 2009, an estimated 285 million individuals were afflicted with diabetes. This figure surged to 425 million in 2017. In 2019 alone, an estimated 463 million cases were recorded and is projected to escalate to 642 million by 2040. Urban regions report a notably higher diabetes prevalence (10.8%) compared to their rural counterparts (7.2%) (5)(6). In Pakistan, diabetes mellitus has emerged as a growing public health issue. The current prevalence of type-2 diabetes mellitus stands at 11% within the country. Among males, the prevalence is approximately 11.2%, while among females, it is 9.19%.(7). In 2021 IDF reported that Pakistan has the 3rd highest number of people having diabetes with 33 million adults affected, following China (141 million) and India (74 million) and responsible for 400,000 deaths in Pakistan (8).

Key contributors to this situation include a complex combination of genetic, environmental factors larger population size, lack of physical activity and change of lifestyle, obesity, and overweight. The use of unhealthy food is also an effector of diabetes mellitus (DM) Thus it is extremely important to find out those factors which reduce the risk of type 2 diabetes. SSB is one of these factors that are responsible for obesity and type 2 diabetes, reduction in the usage of SSB can be correlated with reducing the risk of developing type 2 diabetes(9). Based on observational studies a diet producing a low glycemic response is associated with a lower prevalence of metabolic disorder, type 2 diabetes and coronary artery disease than a portion of food having a high glycemic response(10)(11) . However, many individuals with diabetes may not

realize the complications arising from poorly managed blood glucose level (12).

The concept of glycemic index (GI) emerged from the observation that different foods with equivalent weights of carbohydrates can lead to markedly different blood glucose responses, proposed by Jenkins and his colleagues (13)(14). The GI is defined as the postprandial blood glucose response obtain by a given amount of food that contains 50 g (or in some cases 25 g) of available carbohydrate, expressed as a percentage of that elicited by 50 g (or 25 g) of the reference carbohydrate (glucose solution or white bread) in the same subject. The GI is, hereby, set at 100 for the reference product, and the values of the test product are expressed relative to this (1)(15). In other words, the glycemic index is a qualitative indicator of the ability of carbohydrates to raise blood glucose levels(16). The GI ranks carbohydrate-containing foods based on their speed of elevating blood glucose and glycemic response. High GI foods, like bread, rapidly break down and are swiftly absorbed, leading to elevated blood sugar levels and increased insulin response. Conversely, low GI foods digest slowly, resulting in a gradual impact on glucose levels and insulin response (17)(18). Methodologically GI is a measure of the Percentage of the incremental area under the curve (iAUC) concerning 2 hours' blood glucose level following the ingestion of a test diet compared with a standard diet (usually glucose or bread) (19).GI is expressed as a low, medium, and high, variations exist in literature as to what constitutes a low GI and high GI diet(11). Diets having a GI of less than 55 are referred to as low GI food and a diet having a GI between 56-69 are intermediate GI diet and a GI of more than 70 are high GI diet(14) . In Pakistan very little information regarding the GI of local foods is available (20).

The notion of glycemic load (GL) was introduced to describe simultaneously the quality (GI) and quantity of carbohydrates in a food serving. It is calculated as GI multiply by total number of serving carbohydrates in grams and then divide by 100(21). To quantify the overall glycemic effect of standard portion size of food the concept of GL is used. GL values are categorized as: a diet having $GL > 20$ is considered as high, 11-19 GL is intermediate and $GL < 10$ is considered as low GL(1). Reducing the GL of the diet may be a valuable

method to enhance glycemic control in peoples with type 2 diabetes mellitus or pre diabetic patients. Reduction in GL can be attain by increasing the usage of dietary fiber and decreasing the usage of moderate and high GI foods intake such as white bread(21).

According to the CORDEX ALIMENTARIUS commission definition, dietary fiber is an edible carbohydrate polymer that is impervious to an endogenous digestive enzyme and thus cannot be absorbed nor hydrolyzed in small intestine (22). Studies suggest that one simple way to live with diabetes easier is to increase fiber intake because it lowers the GI of other foods (13). Dietary fibers are classified on basis of primary food source, chemical structure, solubility, and viscosity. Dietary fibers are divided into two types insoluble and soluble. Insoluble forms of dietary fiber like cellulose etc. produce bulking effect on feces while the most soluble form of fiber like psyllium does not contribute to fecal bulking in contrast to insoluble fibers. Soluble fiber form gel in the intestine and can delay the absorption of glucose and fats hence lowering the GI and GL of food (23). Both lower GI, and lower GL scores are associated with decreased inflammation, cancer risk, and chronic diseases (24).

Currently, there are only a few publications about GI and GL of local Pakistani food and drinking items. So it's necessary to find the GI and GL of common Pakistani food and beverages so that we can provide the local population with recommendations for a healthy diet that has low GI and GL. For this purpose, Jam-e-Shirin has taken which is a common Pakistani beverage. This study will also check the effect of fiber ispaghula husk (Psyllium Husk) on the GI and GL of Jam-e-Shirin.

METHODOLOGY:

A total of 15 healthy male individuals, with a mean age of 22 ± 0.83 years, were recruited from Khyber Medical University for this non-blind interventional study with repeat measures. The study took place in the laboratory of the Institute of Paramedical Sciences, Khyber Medical University, Peshawar, over a duration of six months. Inclusion criteria encompassed individuals with a Body Mass Index (BMI) falling within the range of 18.5 - 24.5 kg/m², fasting blood glucose levels between 75-100 mg/dL, non-smokers, and those devoid of any genetic or

metabolic disorders. Conversely, individuals categorized as obese, smokers, or alcohol consumers, those with a family history of diabetes, and those taking medications that may influence postprandial glucose levels were excluded from the study. The test meals employed in the study were Jam-e Shirin and fiber, with Glaxose-D glucose serving as the reference standard. Before the commencement of the study, all participants received comprehensive information about its various aspects. Subsequently, participants were screened for diabetes, smoking habits, or chronic conditions that could impact the study. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Ethical Committee of Khyber Medical University.

The study was executed across three distinct days. On the day prior to the tests, participants were advised to refrain from engaging in any physical activities. On the first day, after an overnight fast of 10-12 hours, blood was collected in sodium fluoride tubes (gray top) for glucose measurement. Subsequently, each individual was administered a solution containing 25g of glucose in 300 ml of water, after which they were instructed to abstain from any physical activity for a period of two hours. Blood samples were then collected at 15-minute intervals over the course of 120 minutes. Glucose levels were determined using a spectrophotometer. On the second day, fasting blood glucose levels were measured for all participants. Following this, a solution comprising 33ml of Jam-e-Shirin (equivalent to 25g of glucose) dissolved in 300 ml of water was administered to each participant. Blood glucose levels were then measured at 15-minute intervals for the subsequent 120 minutes. On the third day, participants were divided into three groups, each consisting of five individuals. Fiber was dissolved in 33ml of Jam-e Shirin solution, with Group 1, Group 2, and Group 3 receiving 2.5g, 5g, and 10g of fiber, respectively. Prior to administering the test food to the groups, baseline fasting glucose levels were determined. Blood glucose levels were subsequently measured at 15-minute intervals for 120 minutes.

Upon completion of data collection, graphs were generated for reference glucose, Jam-e-Shirin, and fiber mixed with Jam-e-Shirin to calculate the incremental area under the curve (iAUC) using Microsoft Excel. The iAUC was determined using the trapezoid method to obtain the GI and GL of the test

foods. Data analysis was performed using the Paired T-Test in SPSS.

RESULT:

A total of 15 male participants with normal BMI and blood pressure were enrolled in the study. On the first day, the mean fasting blood glucose level of all

participants was determined to be 95. Subsequently, participants ingested 25g of reference glucose, resulting in blood glucose levels of 129, 149, 112, 96, and 89 at 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes respectively and iAUC was computed using the trapezoid method from the graph, as illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure-1: Comparison of mean blood glucose in Jam e shirin to blood glucose with standard

The iAUC for the reference glucose level was determined to be 2251 mg/dl*sec. This value provided the GI and GL as 100 and 25, respectively, as detailed in **Table 1**. On the second day, post-ingestion of 33ml of Jam-e-Shirin, the mean blood glucose concentrations at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes were recorded at 95, 137, 140, 101, 92, and

90, respectively. Notably, the peak glucose level was observed at 30 minutes, subsequently declining below baseline levels at 90 and 120 minutes. The iAUC for Jam-e-Shirin was calculated as 1863.23 mg/dl*sec from the graph illustrated in **Figure 1**. Additionally, the corresponding GI and GL were determined to be 82.77 and 20.69, respectively, as outlined in **Table 2**.

Table no-1: iAUC, GI, and GL of reference glucose and jam e Shirin without fiber.

Reference glucose

S.no	Variable	Results
1	iAUC	2251mg/dl*sec
2	GI	100
3	GL	25g

Jam e Shirin without fiber

S.no	Variable	Results
1	iAUC	1863.23mg/dl*sec
2	GI	82.77
3	GL	20.69g

Prior to introducing dietary fiber, participants were stratified into three groups, each comprising five male participants. Group 1 received Jam-e-Shirin enriched with 2.5 grams of dietary fiber, exhibiting mean blood glucose levels of 91, 113, 116, 89, 83, and 86 at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes, respectively. The corresponding iAUC was 959.9 mg/dl*sec, resulting in a GI and GL of 42.63 and 10.64 grams, respectively (Table 2). In Group 2, after consuming Jam-e-Shirin enriched with 5 grams of dietary fiber, blood glucose concentrations at the mentioned intervals were 96,

118, 125, 98, 90, and 84. The resulting iAUC was 1114.38 mg/dl*sec, yielding a GI and GL of 49.49 and 12.36 grams, respectively (Table 2). For Group 3, following the ingestion of Jam-e-Shirin containing 10 grams of dietary fiber, blood glucose concentrations were assessed at the specified time points, yielding values of 94, 109, 117, 104, 94, and 91. The iAUC for 10 grams of dietary fiber was determined as 1045.48 mg/dl*sec, resulting in a GI and GL of 46.42 and 11.60 grams, respectively (Table 2).

Table no-2: iAUC, GI, GL of different gram of fiber with jam e Shirin.

Jam e Shirin with 2.5 gram of fibers

S.no	Variable	Results
1	iAUC	959.9mg/dl*sec
2	GI	42.63
3	GL	10.64g

Jam e Shirin with 5 gram of fiber

S.no	Variable	Results
1	iAUC	1114.38mg/dl*sec
2	GI	49.49
3	GL	12.36g

Jam e Shirin with 10 gram of fiber

S.no	Variable	Results
1	iAUC	1045.48mg/dl*sec
2	GI	46.42
3	GL	11.60g

Following the acquisition of GI and GL data for Jam-e-Shirin with and without dietary fiber (isphagula husk), statistical analysis was performed using SPSS paired T-test to elucidate the impact of varying fiber quantities on Jam-e-Shirin within participants. The results revealed 2-tailed significance levels of 0.01, 0.02, and 0.01 for GI and GL in groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively, as outlined in Table 3. All three groups exhibited p-values below 0.05, signifying a notable influence on reducing the GI and GL of Jam-e-Shirin.

Furthermore, the mean difference analysis indicated that Group 2, supplemented with 5.0g of fiber, demonstrated a slightly greater reduction in GI and GL compared to Group 1(2.5g) and Group 3 (10g). These findings highlight that 5.0g of fiber exerts a more pronounced effect in diminishing the GI and GL of Jam-e-Shirin, in comparison to both 2.5g and 10g, based on the mean difference metrics provided in Table 3.

Table no-3: pre and post fiber glycemic index and glycemic load of different gram of fiber.

Pre and post fiber glycemic index							
S.no	Different gram of fiber	Pre fiber		Post fiber		Results	
		mean(g)	SD	mean(g)	SD	T value	Sig(2-tailed)
1	2.5 grams	77.09	±18.1	42.63	±16.91	4.19	0.01

2	5.0 grams	88.84	±19.1	49.49	±15.18	3.66	0.02
3	10 grams	82.27	±18.6	46.42	±12.44	8.50	0.01
Pre and post fiber glycemic load							
1	2.5grams	19.27	±4.53	10.64	±4.23	4.19	0.01
2	5.0 grams	22.20	±4.78	12.36	±3.79	3.67	0.02
3	10 grams	20.56	±4.65	11.60	±3.12	8.54	0.01

DISCUSSION:

The GI and GL of food are pivotal factors in managing hyperglycemia, particularly for individuals with diabetes or those at risk of developing it, as well as in mitigating the likelihood of associated hyperglycemia-related conditions. Limited information exists regarding the GI and GL values of commonly consumed Pakistani beverages. To address this gap, our study focused on investigating the impact of dietary fiber on the GI and GL of Jam-e-Shirin, a widely consumed beverage in Pakistan, accounting for approximately 60% of beverage consumption.

Similar study conducted by Nebiyu Dereje et.al. they find GI and GL of commonly used Ethiopian foods. The study aimed to find the GI and GL of Corn Injera, White Wheat Bread and Teff Injera, and taken as test food, and glucose was taken as a reference food. After consumption of test food blood glucose was determined at 0min, 15min, 30min, 60min, 90min, and 120min. From data, the GI of Teff Injera, White Wheat Bread, and Corn Injera were 36, 46(which is considered as low), and 97(high), and the glycemic load was 7(low), 14(moderate), 22(high), respectively. The GI and GL of Teff Injera are considered much lower compared with White Wheat Bread (p=0.03) and Corn Injera (p<0.001). The findings of the study show that Teff Injera and White Wheat Bread have low GI and GL so it is recommended for diabetic patients to be consumed while Corn Injera is not recommended for any type of diabetic or pre-diabetic patients (25).

There is another study conducted by Ryan D. Francis that investigate the GI and GL of vegetable drinks (Cucumber-Cucumis sativus, carrot-Daucus Carota, Beetroot-Beta vulgaris) are taken as test food and 25 grams of carbohydrate was taken as reference glucose. A total 10 healthy participants were selected to the study. The study design was non blind, cross over trials. First the participants were given reference

glucose (25 grams) after that they were served with test food (which contain equal amount of carbohydrate as reference glucose) then blood glucose level was determined at 0min, 15min, 30min, 60min, 90min, 120min. After that the GI and GL of vegetable dinks were determined geometrically by expressing the incremental area under blood glucose curve as percentage of each subject averages iAUC for the standard food. The GI and GL of vegetable drinks is 34±10 and 4.4 respectively which are classified under low glycemic food (1).

In our study, participants were categorized into three groups, each receiving Jam-e-Shirin with varying fiber content. The GI and GL values were determined for each group, resulting in GI and GL values of 42.63 and 10.64g for Group 1 (2.5 grams of fiber), 49.49 and 12.36g for Group 2 (5 grams of fiber), and 46.42 and 11.6g for Group 3 (10 grams of fiber), respectively. These findings clearly demonstrate that the addition of fiber to Jam-e-Shirin significantly reduces both its GI and GL values, underscoring the potential of dietary fiber to mitigate the glycemic impact of this commonly consumed beverage.

Another type of study examined the impact of dietary fiber on postprandial blood glucose levels in healthy adult participants. The study select 50 healthy participants, and 50 grams of glucose were taken as a reference food. After consumption of reference glucose without dietary fiber the blood glucose level was determined at 0min, 30min, 60min, and 120min. The mean blood glucose (mmol/l) with standard deviation was 4.33±0.50 at fasting, 8.28±0.74 after 30 minutes, and 6.75±0.61 after 60 minutes, and 5.24±0.59 after 120 minutes. The mean blood glucose (mmol/l) and standard deviation were measured again after the addition of dietary fiber with reference glucose. The mean blood glucose at fasting was 4.40±0.56, after 30 minutes 6.46±0.63, after 60 minutes 5.68±0.66, and after 120 minutes 4.60±0.55.

So the findings of the study show that the mean blood postprandial blood glucose concentration sufficiently decreases at 30min, 60min, and 120min both with dietary and without dietary fibers. However, the mean postprandial blood glucose concentration was significantly ($p < 0.001$) decreased at 30, 60, and 120 min with the addition of dietary fiber (26).

This study elucidates the notable influence of common Pakistani beverage Jam-e-Shirin on GI and GL and highlights the considerable reduction in these parameters achievable by incorporating varying quantities of dietary fiber into Jam-e-Shirin. Nevertheless, our study is constrained by the examination of a single test beverage. Hence, we recommend future research with larger sample sizes and a more extensive investigation of commonly consumed foods in Pakistan, encompassing fast foods, carbonated beverages, and staple items like French fries, for a more comprehensive assessment.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of our study show that the GI and GL of jam e shirin is 82.77 and 20.69g respectively. The GI and GL of jam e shirin can be significantly reduced by adding different grams of fiber i.e. (2.5, 5, 10g). 5.0 gram has greater impact followed by 2.5 grams and 10 grams on reducing GI and GL. So we can recommend the usage of dietary fiber with different type of beverages to prevent population from becoming pre diabetic and diabetic.

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